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Community policing and security management in Nigeria: A study of Abuja arterial routes and satellite settlements-Lugbe and Chika

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Abstract

The pattern of policing in Nigeria is still at the abysmal stage as many still see the police as enemies while the police are still overtly caught on tape, daily abusing and infringing the rights of citizens and extorting them whether on traffic, in motor parks or at police stations. This study leveraged on structural functionalism theory to interrogate the nexus between community policing and security management in Nigeria. The study focused on the Abuja arterial routes and satellite settlements of Lugbe and Chika. Study employed survey research design through a structured five point Likert scale questionnaire to elicit responses from 400 respondents as guided by Taro Yamane sampling technique. The study analysis tool was the ordinary least squares simple linear regression technique. Finding from the study revealed that community policing has significant impact on security management in Nigeria. The Study concluded that Intelligence gathering and surveillance must be constantly undertaken, which is important in order to ensure that law enforcement agents are proactive and can reasonably predict potential insecurity threats with near perfect accuracy rather than being reactive. The study recommends that government must devote attention to security intelligence, capacity-building to meet the global best practice and acquisition of modern technology. This will be attainable when the culture of good governance that makes responsiveness and accountability to the community a norm, particularly by law enforcement agencies.

Keywords: Community Policing; Security management; Structural Functionalism Theory

1. Introduction

Community policing focuses on solving problems, which requires regular contacts with citizens and measures success in terms of reduction of fear of crime, visibility of security officers as deterrence, reduction in neighborhood disorder, and crime rate reduction. It directly addresses the need to restructure and refocus police officer selection, training, evaluation, and promotion. This pattern of policing though still developing, but is still very much at an abysmal stage in the Nigerian context as many still see the police as enemy while the police is still overtly caught on bureaucratic overloads, infringing the rights of citizens and wanton extortions.

In the early 20th century, the rise of automobiles, telecommunications and suburbanization transformed how the police operated. Researchers have said that the police moved towards reactive strategies rather than proactive, focusing on answering emergency calls quickly and relying on motor vehicle patrols to deter crime. Some police department began rotating officers between different neighborhoods as a measure to prevent corruption and, as a result, foot patrols became rare. This changed the nature of police presence in many neighborhoods (Skogan, 2000).

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Efforts to repair relations between police forces and the community due to the apparent distrust of the police by many community members, especially along racial lines, suggested developing a new type of police officer, who would act as a community liaison and work to build bridges between law enforcement and minority populations. (Mungadi et al., 2021). Such that aimless motor patrols are seen as no longer an effective deterrence to crime (Kelling, et al., 1974). Hence, this suggested that police officers spent so much time on response duties and in cars that they had become isolated from their communities. This development led policing to what would later become known as "community policing"(Travis, 2008).

In Nigeria, precisely April 2019, President Muhammadu Buhari, approved the adoption of Community Policing to tackle the upsurge of crime in Nigeria (Vanguard, 2020), with many stakeholders clamoring for it, on the assumption that it is the long-awaited solution to stem the tide of insecurity. The drives, was to take Policing closer to members of the public and by extension, get prompt information that could help them to be proactive. With the prevailing security challenges evidenced in the escalation of violent conflicts and crimes from herdsmen-farmers clashes, and insurgency in North-East, the resurgence of militancy in the Niger Delta and kidnapping for ransom in the South West and other regions, the need for a strategic policing approach has since become expedient.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Conceptual Issues

2.1.1. Crime and Community-policing

Crime is an illegal action society punishes through the government's legal system. It is therefore an offense against public law. Put differently, crime is the intentional commission of an act usually deemed socially harmful or dangerous and specifically defined, prohibited and punishable under criminal law. Community policing is a strategy of policing that focuses on developing relationships and partnership with community members. It is a philosophy of full-service policing that is highly personal, where an officer patrols the same area for a period of time and develops a partnership with citizens to identify and solve problems. The fundamental objective or goal of community policing is for police to build relationships with the community, including local agencies to reduce crime and social disorder.

2.1.2. Security and Security Management

Security is seen as the condition of not being threatened, whether physically, psychologically, emotionally, financially or materially. Insecurity is lack of security of, safety, life, subsistence, health care, education, water, roads, properties and family. It is the state of being subject to danger and vulnerability. Security management on the other hand, is seen structurally, as the identification of state's capability in deploying the internal security framework to collecting intelligence and harnessing national assets; of human, technology and the environment, followed by the documentation and implementation of policies and procedures for protecting these assets and interest from threat and vulnerabilities. An informed security management could be seen where roles of all formal and informal security agencies are well captured in the State security architecture, as this will situate security more closer to the people as against a centralised security architecture as being practiced in Nigeria (Afuzie, 2023)

2.1.3. An Overview of Community Policing in Nigeria

The concept of policing in Nigeria is an age long system especially since the emergence of the modern-day state system. Meanwhile this is not to say that the pre-colonial African societies lacked internal security mechanisms to keep the societies safe, as several local guards and age grades were commissioned to secure the society (Obar, 2019). In the old phase of the post-colonial era, the earlier concept of community policing initiative resulted in the formation of vigilante groups in every nook and cranny of the country. Ethnic militias as vigilante groups emerged in communities and cities across the country, ostensibly to combat rising crime waves in the face of the inability of the police to effectively deal with armed robbery and other violent crimes (vanguard report, 2020). Some of the early groups include:

Operation Sunlight

The very first of such operations began around 1988 when 'Operation Sunlight.' Was introduced. The operation was made up of detectives and vigilante groups with a mandate to arrest and prosecute robbery suspects. Apparently, the government found the judicial process rather slow and boring. The government later reconstituted the squad to form another outfit code-named "Operation Damisa" (Hausa word for leopard) made up of men drawn from the army, the police and civil defence groups who acted as informants.

Operation Zaki

This code-name, assigned to a brutal hit squad comprised of the army and civilian vigilante groups set up by the military government of Borno State in response to the menace of armed robbery in the state. Its mandate was to shoot at sight any person (rightly or wrongly) suspected to be a robber. The mass killing of people in the name of Operation Zaki continued in spite of the protest from human rights organizations and other concerned members of the public.

O' dua People Congress (OPC)

The OPC was formed during the dark and brutal era of repressive military dictatorship presided over by General Sani Abacha. It was an ethnic response to the perceived persecution of Yoruba people under the military regime. This persecution was believed to have culminated in the annulment of June 12, 1993 presidential election apparently won by late Chief M.K. O. Abiola. Core to the formation of OPC was the demand for a Sovereign National Conference, to address issues of marginalization and oppression. Over time OPC began to meddle into vigilante activities and became effective in using unorthodox means to fish out and eliminate criminals. For this reason, the group often clashed with the Police, who accused OPC of usurping Police constitutional functions and excesses of resorting to lawless methods and killing innocent people. The OPC equally accuse the Police of colluding with and aiding criminals, as suspects arrested were released.

The Bakassi boys

Historically, Bakassi evolved when armed robbery rose to a level unprecedented in the history of Abia State, as the Police was unable to protect lives and property in the commercial town. The traders who were the worst victims then set up a resistance force that countered, the armed robbers and the Mafia, of which the Bakassi boys triumphed. The group organized themselves into a citizen-initiated vigilante group such that, suspected criminals who hitherto freely menaced the city and its environs were fished out, "tried in the Bakassi "Court" and those convicted had their arms, legs, and head chopped off with machetes or before being burnt. Normalcy returned to the commercial town as criminal reportedly fled to neighbouring cities (Irom, 2019).

The Egbesu boys

The Egbesu boys were the first real attempt at community policing in the Niger Delta area of Nigeria. Before the formation of the group, the Niger-Delta area witnessed a lot of crises; of youth restiveness manifesting in cases of kidnapping and hostage-taking of oil workers. These crises centered on the effects of oil exploration, exploitation and demand for resource control and compensation by the people of the Niger-Delta. The causes of youth restiveness in the Niger Delta included lack of youth development programmes by government, activities of multinational companies; lack of youth participation in policy and decision making; poverty, unemployment, oppression and marginalization; insensitivity of government to demands of the youth; mistrust of elders; environmental pollution; domination by major ethnic groups, unitary nature of Nigeria's political system and lack of control of natural resources. All these, necessitated the birth of the Egbesu Boys.

In Lagos, armed policemen were attached to members of these vigilante groups, who carry out surveillance of crime-prone areas and this symbiotic relationship, allow Police to gradually win the confidence of members of the public in information gathering. An attestation was ending the reign of terror of the Badoo cult group in Lagos State (Iregbenu & Uzonwanne, 2015).

There were also establishment of state-owned security outfits to drive home the debate on Community Policing, with retired senior security personnel assigned to head them. The Neighborhood Watch which has been in existence in Lagos was upgraded to the Lagos Neighborhood Safety Corps (LNSC), where residents of a particular area were mandated to watch over the area, make an arrest when necessary and hand culprits over to Police divisions in their localities (Shittu et al., 2023). A similar outfit, "The Rivers State Neighborhood Safety Corps Agency (RIVNESCA), had 3,000 persons recruited into it, with a charge to bridge the security gap in the state.

Community Policing and Traditional Policing

Many community-oriented police structures focus on assigning officers to a specific area called a "beat", during this officer become familiar with that area through a process of "beat profiling". (Prenzler & Sarre, 2020). "Traditional policing" is used to describe policing styles that were predominant before modern community policing movements, or in police forces which have not adopted them. The response-centered style has also been called "fire brigade policing" in the UK (Robert, 2016). Community policing could be seen as a restoration of an earlier ideology, which had been overshadowed by reactive policing after the rise of automobiles and telecommunications (Brogden, 1987).

The goal of traditional policing is to protect law-abiding citizens from criminals. It reflects a "popular desire for justice and order through any means necessary" (Auregui, 2013). She says police do this by identifying and apprehending criminals while gathering enough evidence to convict them. Traditional beat officers' approach on duty is to respond to incidents swiftly, and clear emergency calls as quickly as possible. (Beatrice, 2013). Some researchers argue that this type of policing does not stop or reduce crime significantly; and say it is simply a temporary fix to a chronic problem where officers are often called to return to the same issue and individuals. (Travis, 2008). The structure of the community policing organization differs in that police assets are refocused with the goals of specific, written rules to give more creative problem-solving techniques to the police officer to provide alternatives to traditional law enforcement (Cordner, 2010).

In contrast, community policing's main goal is to assist the public in establishing and maintaining a safe, orderly social environment. While apprehending criminals is one important goal of community policing, it is not the only goal. Community policing is concerned with solving the crimes that the community is concerned about by working with and gaining support from the security agencies (Adelani et al., 2023). Studies have shown, that the most effective methods include dialogue between police, government resources, citizens, and local business to address the problems affecting the community (Mungadi et al., 2021). Police communicate with the community in variety of ways, including polls or surveys, town meetings, call-in programs, community sport and fatigue exercises, and meetings with interest groups. They use these connections to understand what the community wants out of its police officers and what the community is willing to do to solve its crime problem.

2.2. Benefits of Community Policing

Several benefits of community policing have been discussed, but a few is identified below;

- It increases security personnel and their agencies accountability to the community
- Residents having a more favorable view of their local security agencies/department.
- Presence of security personnel serves as crime deterrence
- Improved trust between law enforcement and residents.
- More accurate information from residents regarding criminal activity in their community.
- Better understanding of the needs of citizens and their expectations of the policed.

Implications of security challenges to national stability

- Widespread insecurity affects business investment as problems resulting from insecurity have a damaging consequence of giving signal to the rest of the international community that a territory is not safe and secure, and as such not suitable for economic investment and activities.
- Widespread discontent and loss of confidence in the system have their ways of affecting national political stability. Most importantly, constant violence in the country will impinge on the continued existence of Nigeria democracy.
- Insecurity in Nigeria has not only impacted unhelpfully on Nigeria's image in the international community, it has also threatened Nigeria's unity and cooperate existence (Afuzie, 2022).
- Insecurity leads to underdevelopment with increased budgetary allocation targeted at ensuring security. Funds for development are diverted to acquisition of weapons and military hardware to fight crime and insurgency.

2.3. Community Policing as a Strategy for Internal Security Management in Nigeria

The idea of finding the best policing practices in Nigeria led to the establishment of the community policing initiative. this is as a result of the gradual failure of the initial traditional policing system in Nigeria, otherwise known as "Reactive Policing Technique", where by the Police action commences after an offence might have been committed (Idris, 2019). Nigeria's adoption and implementation of Community policing dated back to 27th April 2004. The goal is to have the people to actively take part in policing their communities in partnership with the Police. Through partnership, law enforcement agencies will be able to know most security concerns of the people and address them in a holistic manner.

Interestingly, two reasons for adopting a more proactive approach which are inherent in commuting policing are both philosophical and pragmatic. At the philosophical level, any police organization that's seeks to serve democratic and humanitarian ideals must be seen to be transparent, fair, apolitical, accountable and responsive to public perception and expectations Idris (2019). These ideas as espoused in the philosophical level of analysis further complicates the idea of idea of community policing as the men of the Nigeria Police Force are perceived lacking in most if not all of these

democratic principles of transparency and accountability. This complacent professional conduct has resulted in the difficulty of the community in trusting the people both with information and cooperation (Bassey, 2019).

2.4. Predictors of Community Policing

2.4.1. Visible and Accessibility

The visibility of law enforcement agent would mean that selected patrol officers are assigned permanently to small areas (beats) and as such patrols are to provide public assurances, these assurances is a visible deterrence to crime. The presence of such assigned officers serves as a form of target hardening. Such assigned officers also bonded with the primary beat area (Shittu et al., 2022).

2.4.2. Presence of Community Consultation, Cooperation and Interdependence

The police collaborate with the public at large in identifying and prioritizing community needs. The police and community work in partnership to devise and implement agreed solutions to problems. The community actively engages in policing role through volunteer schemes initiating neighborhood and augmenting police patrol services.

2.4.3. Multi-agency Collaboration

The security agencies reality and recognition that no statutory or voluntary body can make meaningful impact on social problems if it acts in isolation of others. The police liaise with and work with together with other statutory agencies and volunteer organization in addressing crime and other disturbances to public tranquility.

2.4.4. Community Policing means Accountability

This requisite of community policing demands that law enforcement management are open and accountable about policies, strategies, operations and decisions affecting the community. This equally translates that all police personnel are accountable for their professional and personal standards and for their treatment of citizens. The controls emplace should elicit policing effectiveness monitored, evaluated and open to public scrutiny and also citizens with a grievance against the Police have a means of redress.

2.5. Theoretical Framework

2.5.1. Structural-Functionalism Theory

Structural functionalism which emerged in the mid-twentieth century, is an orientation that focuses on structure- the patterning of roles, the form of institutions, and the overall articulation of institutions in a society – and seeks to explain these structures in terms of their functions – contributions to the stability and persistence of societies. Émile Durkheim is often labeled the first functionalist, and he certainly gave attention to the functions of institutions and even of apparent pathologies such as crime. It was most influential in the post-World War II period (1940s to 1970s) but it still contributes to the conceptualization of society (Garner, 2019).

Structural analysis means that society is viewed in terms of the patterning of roles, relationships, and institutions. Functionalism means that the existence, persistence, and form of institutions can be explained in terms of their contribution to the stability of society. Institutions and society, not the individual, are at the center of the analysis. All societies need to accomplish certain tasks, to meet specific imperatives, in order to continue to exist as coherent societies; the term “societal needs and requisites” sums up the functional approach (Turner & Maryanski, 1988).

Protagonists of structural-functional framework of analysis; August Comte, Herbert Spencer, Malinowski and Radcliffe-Brown, Parsons (1937, 1961); Merton (1957); Davis (1959); Evans-Pritchard (1940); Meyer Fortes (1945) are basically concerned with the phenomenon of system maintenance and regulation. The basic theoretical proposition of this approach is that all systems exist to perform functions through their structures since the functioning of any political system may also be viewed in terms of its capabilities, which is the way it performs as a unit in its environment. Antagonism to this theory at the emergence of conflict theorists; Davis and Moore (1945) and Tumin (1953); charged that structural functionalist theory had become a conservative legitimating ideology for a profoundly unequal status quo of class exploitation and racial hegemony.

The theory stresses that all systems have structures, which can be identified, and those structures perform specific set of tasks if they are to remain in existence and maintain their relevance to the system. Structural-functional analysis will enable us to establish the relevance of the structures created by government to help maintain order in the whole system.

Structural-Functionalism as a theoretical framework is intended to explain the basis for the maintenance of order and stability in society and the relevant arrangements within the society, which maintain the social order and stability.

2.5.2. Empirical Studies

Adelani et al. (2023) leveraged on gap theory to interrogate impact of community policing on security management in Kubwa, Bwari area council FCT-Abuja in Nigeria. This study decomposed community policing into interconnectedness between the Nigeria Law Enforcement Agencies with the host community and accommodation of private and informal security providers into the Nigeria Security architecture. This study employed an exploratory research design with reliance on publicly available archive documents. The study relies solely on secondary data. Results that emanated from the study submitted that poor interconnectedness between the Nigeria Law Enforcement Agencies with the very community they set out to protect remain an albatross to the evolvement of community policing, which is further complicated by Nigeria's Security architecture which study alleged is too unitary hence its inability to incorporate the private security providers, and other informal security actors in addressing insecurity.

Isa et al. (2021) studied the challenges and prospects of community policing and national security in Nigeria. The method of data analysis was qualitative. The major findings of the study were that the 1999 Constitution frameworks and Nigeria's defense policy will be the major challenges to the implementation of community policing in Nigeria. Also, Bello et al. (2016) took an overview of community policing in Nigeria. They identified three strategies that made community policing quite distinct from traditional policing: community partnership, organizational transformation, and problem-solving. Study reviewed challenges community policing faced amongst the Police Force, community, and those emanating from the government. Study concluded that the need for an integrated effort from all structures; reorientation programs for the police and the community, fighting corruption, and to ensure that the rule of law is obeyed by the police, community and the political leaders.

In a research study conducted by Ngwu and Ahuruonye (2017) on the efficacy of community policing in Nigeria, the study focused on the concept of community policing and its effectiveness in "order maintenance", crime prevention and fear reduction in the community as opposed to the traditional focusing prosecution of serious street crimes based on jungle justice. The study highlighted the performances of both the formal security agent (the police) and the informal security agent (Neighbourhood watch/vigilante group). It was revealed that police corruption, brutality, insensitivity, high-handedness, extortionist tendencies, rudeness, ignorance among others, and on the part of informal group deviating from their original duty scheduled by taking unilateral actions, such as, meddling with husband and wife issues, aligning with politicians to unleash terror on their political, business or other opposers in the community, debt collectors and so on. The former attitude resulted in lack of cooperation with the police and the public in giving the police information or crime situation in their respective communities.

Bello (2019) examined community policing as a correlate of effective security in Oyo State, Nigeria. He opined that the incessant incidents of breakdown of law and order as well as the persistent threats to life and property have shown the lapses in the regular policing system in Nigeria. This trend, therefore, led to the introduction of community policing approach in Oyo State in February, 2004 as an alternative strategy to ensure effective security in the State. The quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson product moment correlation and multiple regression at 0.05 level of significance while qualitative data were content analyzed. It was found that community policing has good correlation with security management in Oyo State.

Osayekemwen and Adeoluwa (2022) investigated the involvement of community members in community policing in Nigeria. The study used a descriptive research approach and used Odeomu in Osun State's Ayadaade Local Government Area as a case study. Both qualitative and quantitative methodologies were used in the investigation. The multistage sampling strategy was adapted from non-probability methods in this study. The data gathered for this investigation were analyzed qualitatively as well as quantitatively. The study concluded that community policing is becoming a more popular strategy for ensuring Nigeria's long-term peace and security.

3. Material and method

To determine the effect of community policing on security management in Nigeria, the survey research design was adopted. The choice of the design was influenced by the nature of the study which was both descriptive and analytical. Also, the geographical area of the study was well defined and the respondents who possess the required information were clearly identified which enabled the use of survey tools so as to gather data for the study in order to establish cause-effect relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variables. The study focuses on the effect of community policing on security management in Lugbe and Chika, Abuja-Nigeria. The estimated population of Abuja

in 2021 was 3,464,000 at the estimated growth rate of 5.67 percent per annum (NPC, 2021). Taro Yamane formula was used to select the sample size and to avoid bias. The Taro’s formula is expressed thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

- n = sample size
- N = population size
- e = tolerable error (0.05)
- 1 = constant

Substituting the values in the above formula we have:

$$\begin{aligned} & 3,464,000/1+3,464,000 (0.05)^2 \\ & = 3,464,000/1+3,464,000 (0.0025) \\ & = 399.9538 \\ & \mathbf{=400} \end{aligned}$$

In applying the Taro Yamane formula on the population of Abuja (which harbors Lugbe and Chika), the total sample size that best represents the population of the study was 400. In this study, data was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The instrument used was the questionnaire. The secondary data were collected from journals and internet. The researcher adopted the 5-point Likert scale which range from: Strongly Agree (SA) = 5; Agree (A) =4; Undecided (U)= 3; Strongly Disagree (SD) = 2; and Disagree(D) =1. The questionnaire consists of two sections, A and B. Section A basically contains the respondents’ biometrics such as age, gender, educational qualifications etc. Section B comprises of questions related to effect of community policing on security management in Nigeria.

Validity and reliability checks were done on the questionnaire to ascertain the degree to which the measuring instrument measure what it is designed to measure. Two levels of validity were carried out. First, the questionnaire passed through face validity; checked by experts in measurement and evaluation for criticisms and purification. Reliability of the instrument which has to do with consistency of the measuring instrument was carried out through the test-retest method. To establish the reliability of the instrument, the researcher conducted a trial test of the instrument on 100 households, and the reliability index ranges from 0.54-0.80, which is adjudged to be reliable.

3.1. Model specification

The model bears the parameters in which the dependent and independent variables are specified. Thus, the model is stated below:

$$SEM = f(COMPOL).....3.1$$

The above model can transformed as:

$$SEM = b_0 + b_1COMPLO+ Vt.....3.2$$

Where:

- SEM= Security Management
- COMPOL = Community Policing
- b₀ = constant term and
- v_t =a error term.

4. Result

4.1. Data presentation and analysis

The table presented below contains the analytical details relating to the findings from the respondents. Of the 400 questionnaires distributed to the respondents, 391 copies representing 97.8 percent were correctly filled and returned to the researcher, while 9 copies of the questionnaire representing 2.2 percent were not returned by the respondents to the researchers. However, from the above analysis, the 391 was considered to be the workable sample size used in the data analysis and was the true representation of the study population.

4.2. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The table below showed the summary of the responses on the personal data of the respondents.

Table 1 Respondents Demography Table

Sex	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	205	52.4
Female	186	47.6
Total	391	100

Table 2 Respondents Educational Qualification Spread

Educational Qualification	Nos	%
FSLC	164	41.9
SSCE	115	29.4
NCE/ND	58	14.8
Bachelor/HND	32	8.3
Masters & Ph.D	22	5.6
Total	391	100

Table 3 Table of Respondents Age Distribution

Year		
11-20 years	30	7.7
21-30years	144	36.8
31-40years	173	44.2
40years & above	44	11.3
Total	391	100

Source: Field survey, (2022)

From table 4.1, 205 respondents representing 52.4 percent of the total respondents were male while 186 respondents representing 47.6 percent of the total respondents were female. Therefore, it can be affirmed that majority of selected households in the study area were male. On the educational level of respondents, 164 and 115 respondents representing 41.9 and 29.4 percent were FSLC and SSCE holders, respectively. 58 and 32 respondents, representing 14.8 and 8.2 percent of the respondents are NCE/ND and B.Sc./BA/HND holders, while 22 respondents representing 5.6 percent were holders of M.Sc./MA/MBA/Ph.D. This revealed that many of the respondents were FSLC holders.

On the age distribution of the respondents, about 173 respondents representing 44.2 percent of the total respondents are between 31-40 years. 144 respondents representing 36.8 percent of the total respondents falls within the age bracket of 21-30 years, 44 respondents representing 11.3 percent of the total respondents equally were 40 years and above, while 30 respondents representing only 7.7 percent of the total respondents falls within 11-20 years' age bracket. Therefore, it can be affirmed that majority of the respondents are between 31-40 years of age.

4.3. Presentation of Results

Table 4 Dependent variable: SEM

Variable	Coefficient	Std, Error	t-Stat	sign
Constant	0.028	0.024	1.158	0.248
COMPOL	0.101	0.026	3.916	0.000
R-squared	0.774			
Adjusted R-squared	0.771			
F-statistic	329.867	Durbin-Watson stat		2.074

Source: Statistical result from SPSS 22.

The equation regressed community policing (COMPOL) on security management in Nigeria. Thus, from a careful examination of the regression result and related statistics the following facts emerged; the regression coefficient of community policing on security management in Nigeria carries a positive sign and the t-value is statistically significant at 5% level of significance. This implies that a 1 percent rise in community policing will instigate an increase of 0.101 percent in security management in Lugbe and Chika areas of Abuja-Nigeria. This implies that effective community policing will enhance the security management framework of the metropolis.

The R-squared (R^2) or coefficient of determination of 0.771 is instructive and indicates a good fit for the model. Simply put, about 77 percent of the total variation in the dependent variable (SEM) is accounted for by the independent variable in the estimated model. The value of Durbin Watson (DW) statistic is 2.074. The tabulated DW at 5 percent level of significance using 391 observations indicated that the lower limit of Durbin Watson statistic is 1.758 while the upper limit is 1.779. The calculated value (DW) = 2.074 is greater than the upper limit (Du) = 1.779, hence there is no evidence of serial correlation in the estimated model.

5. Discussion

Security management has gradually exited the traditional state-centric method of reactive security to a more vibrant proactive security management system supported by several non-state actors who by their member of the community have become agents of community policing system; a strategy of policing which advocate partnership with communities to advance the quest of improving security of lives and property across the length and breadth of the nation.

From the results, it was found that effective community policing will enhance the security management framework of Lugbe and Chika in Abuja, and Nigeria at large. The findings corroborate the views of Adelani et al. (2023); Bello et al. (2016); Bello (2019) and Osayekemwen & Adeoluwa (2022 who opined that community policing is becoming a more popular strategy for ensuring Nigeria's long-term peace and security, and that community policing has positive correlation with security management in Nigeria and this should be maximised.

6. Conclusion

In order to improve service delivery in community policing and assist government in ensuring security in Nigeria, all hands must be on deck as more than just government efforts would be needed to achieve greater result. Hence, it is recommended that; strengthening of the family unit such as cherished social values which were hitherto inherent in family unit must be reactivated and entrenched. Intelligence gathering and surveillance must be constantly undertaken, to meet the global best practice and acquisition of modern technology and to ensure that law enforcement agents are proactive and can reasonably predict potential insecurity threats with near perfect accuracy rather than being reactive.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

There exist no conflict of interest in the course of this study.

Statement of informed consent

We hereby state that Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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